

Studies in the Complexes of U(IV) and Th(IV) with *o*-anisic acid, *p*-anisic acid and *o*-toluic acid

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U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes with ligand mentioned in the title have been isolated from U(OAc)₄ and Th(OAc)₄. Magnetic susceptibilities, IR and reflectance spectra of U(IV) and IR spectra of Th(IV) complexes have been studied to illustrate their structures.

U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes with chelating ligands such as 8-hydroxyquinolines, quinaldine acid, picolinic acids, pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid, hydroxynaphthoic acids, anthranilic acids and thiophene 2-carboxylic acid have been synthesised and characterised recently¹⁻⁴. In the present work complexes of U(IV) and Th(IV) with the title ligands have been prepared and characterised by IR, reflectance spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

Experimental

U(OAc)₄, Th(OAc)₄, *o*-anisic acid (Fluka), *p*-anisic acid (E. Merk) and *o*-toluic acid (Fluka) were used as such. Ethanol and petroleum ether were purified and dried by usual methods.

Preparation of Complexes

U(OAc)₄ or Th(OAc)₄ and the ligand in 1 : 4 ratio were refluxed in ethanol for about half to two hours, when the complex precipitated. The *o*-anisato complexes were washed with petroleum ether while the other complexes with ethanol. All the complexes were dried in vacuum.

The analytical results and colour of the complexes are given in Table 1. IR spectra of the complexes were recorded in nujol mull on Perkin Elmer 337 Infrared Spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra for U(IV) complexes only have been recorded on a SP-700 spectrophotometer. Similarly magnetic susceptibilities of U(IV) chelates alone were measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance.

Results and Discussion

Thorium(IV) chelates are stable at room temperature but uranium(IV) chelates are oxidised in air or hydrolysed in the presence of moisture. The complexes do not melt but are converted to U₃O₈ and ThO₂ at ~600° and ~850° respectively. These are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. This insolubility may indicate their polymeric nature.

In spectra of the chelates I and II (Table 1) indicate that oxygen atom of the carbonyl group coordinates to U(IV) or Th(IV), Antisymmetric and symmetric stretching carboxyl frequencies in the sodium salt of this acid have been found to occur at 1556 and 1395 cm⁻¹ respectively.⁵ Therefore the

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND IR SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES

Chelate No.	Formula	Colour	% Found (calcd.) U/Th	Band Positions (cm ⁻¹)		ν(UO ²⁺)
				ν _{asym} (OCO) (Na-salt) ^{ref. 5}	ν _{sym} (OCO) (Na-salt) ^{ref. 5}	
I	UO(OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	Grey	42.35 (42.66)	I 1620, 1580 (1556)	1495 (1395)	935
II	ThO(OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	White	42.74 (42.04)	II 1540, 1510	1400	—
III	UO(OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	Green	42.22 (42.66)	III 1590, 1525 (1540)	1450-1300b, (1390)	930
IV	Th(OAc) ₂ (OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	White	37.06 (36.71)	IV 1600, 1545	1470, 1425	—
V	UO(H ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	Grey	45.53 (45.25)	V 1600, 1580 (1582)	1470, 1425 (1403)	935
VI	ThO(OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	White	45.60 (44.72)	VI 1600	1510	—

carboxylate group seems to act as a bidentate in I and II chelates. Similarly in comparison with other corresponding sodium salt frequencies listed in Table 1, the same bidentate nature of the carboxylate group in other chelates is also indicated. A strong band at $\sim 935 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in chelates I, III and V may be due to the presence of UO^{2+} ^{1,6,7}.

The μ_{eff} of 2.75, 1.89 and 1.95 B. M. for chelates I, III and V have been reported. Low values of 1.89 and 1.95 B. M. with respect to the expected value of 2.83 B. M. (spin only) may be attributed to metal-metal interactions, probably due to magnetic exchange, involving oxygen bridging.

TABLE 2—REFLECTANCE SPECTRAL DATA OF URANIUM(IV) CHELATES IN NM

Term	Oxobis(<i>o</i> -anisato) Uranium(IV)	Oxobis(<i>p</i> -anisato) Uranium(IV)	Oxobis(<i>o</i> -toluato) Uranium(IV)
3F_4	1950 w	1925 b	1900 sh
3H_5	1575 s	1600 m	1600 m
3F_3	1410 sh	1400 w	1425 m
3F_4	1125 s	1100 s	1090 s ¹
3H_5	860 w	840 w	860 b
$^3P_0, ^1G_4$	—	780 w	—
1D_2	680 vs	670 s	660 s
3P_1	560 s	550 sh	570 sh
1I_6	480 sh	360 s	490 s
	440 sh		420 w

Reflectance spectra of the chelates I, III and V (Table 2) belong to the strong intensity type on the classification of Gans and Marriage⁸. Spectra are similar to the spectra of U(IV) compounds where U(IV) is eight coordinated¹⁻⁴. The chelates

are polymeric with linkages.

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